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THE RIGHT TO ACCESS (MENTAL) HEALTH CARE

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MENTAL HEALTH AND COGNITION - TWO SIDES OF THE SAME COIN?

Abstract: *Cognition refers to the mental capabilities or thinking skills that allow a person to perceive, acquire, understand, and respond to information from their environment. Cognitive health refers to brain functions such as attention, learning, memory, language, and executive function. This includes higher-order functions, like decision-making, goal-setting, planning, and judgment. Cognitive health as a general term can refer to brain and mental health. Research studies suggest that cognitive deficits significantly contribute to poor mental health and low functional outcomes. Without good cognitive health, there is a risk of mental health problems, and struggles with mental health conditions can affect cognitive well-being. So, cognitive and mental health are interrelated, and cognitive health is a necessary prerequisite for mental health. To preserve and improve cognitive health, it is important to build and sustain cognitive reserve. Higher cognitive and brain reserve may be protective factors for mental health issues.*

Keywords: *cognition, mental health, cognitive reserve, brain health.*

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1. About cognition

Cognition in a broad sense means information processing. Also, cognition or cognitive functioning refers to multiple mental abilities, including attention, memory, remembering, perception, motivation, skilled movements, language, problem-solving, reasoning, and decision-making. Throughout an individual life, cognitive performance changes in response to environmental demands and changes (Morozova et al., 2022). Cognition is the process of receiving and storing information for further use in behavior management (Morozova et al., 2022). It is the ability to perceive and react, to process information, and to make sense of it. It also involves making adequate decisions and generating effective and adaptive behavioral patterns. In other words, better cognitive skills provide a better understanding of the environment to interact with it most efficiently and safely (Morozova et al., 2022).

Cognition commonly refers to the perceptual/gnostic and intellectual aspects of mental functioning (Trivedi, 2006). Among the specific mental abilities that may be assessed in determining the adequacy of preserved cognition are orientation, the ability to learn, solve problems, think abstractly, reasoning, make judgments and decisions, the ability to retain and recall events, mathematical ability, different forms of symbol manipulation, control over primitive reactions and behavior, language use and comprehension, attention, perception and praxis (Trivedi, 2006).

Cognition includes all forms of knowing and awareness, such as perceiving, conceiving, remembering, reasoning, judging, imagining, and problem-solving. Along with affect and conation, it is one of the three traditionally identified components of the mind (VandenBos, 2007). Cognition includes all of the conscious and unconscious processes involved in thinking, perceiving, and reasoning. Cognition examples include paying attention to something in the environment, learning new skills, making decisions, processing language, adapting behavior, sensing and perceiving environmental stimuli, solving problems, and using memory capacity.

During childhood cognition develops, and eventually, cognitive decline occurs as a part of aging. Because central nervous system (CNS)

regeneration processes are imperfect, some cognitive functions may become impaired as a part of normal aging due to neuronal degeneration and death (Morozova et al., 2022).

Higher cognitive ability predicts a lower incidence of psychiatric disorders (Batty et al., 2005) and lower levels of self-rated mental health problems, such as depressive symptoms (Khandaker et al., 2018). Cognitive ability has also been associated with higher psychological well-being measured with concepts such as happiness, positive affect, and life satisfaction (Ali et al., 2013).

Cognitive functions are essential for the normal functioning of every individual, and if they are impaired, everyday life is extremely difficult and unproductive (Morozova et al., 2022). Some domains of cognitive functioning somehow decrease with the presence of mental illness. In other words, some mental health illnesses contribute to a lack or loss of cognitive abilities. However, each psychiatric or neurological disease commonly contributes to a certain cognitive domain disruption.

The mechanisms accounting for the associations between cognitive ability and mental health remain poorly understood. The association between cognition and mental health mainly may be explained by strict biological factors, such as chronic inflammation which has been associated with both mental health and cognitive ability (Khandaker et al., 2018). The mental health associations of cognitive ability might reflect the underlying integrity of the nervous system and the efficiency of information processing. Cognition may be indirectly associated with mental health, to the extent that it is an indicator of “system integrity” (Whalley, Deary, 2001), i.e., integrity of the nervous system, or of its underlying physiological processes that influence mental health. Cognition also may be associated with mental health because it may be part of a causal chain that modifies mental health risk (Hatch et al., 2007). Cognitive development partly determines educational level, social and occupational status, and income (Feinstein, Bynner, 2004; Richards, Sacker, Deary, 2013).

Studies have reported an association between low cognitive ability in childhood or early adulthood and adverse mental health outcomes in mid-adulthood (Batty et al., 2006; Batty et al., 2005). While the reasons for

this association are not fully understood, many dynamically interactive processes may be involved.

Also, some studies claim that children and adolescents with high cognitive abilities (called gifted children) have sometimes been portrayed as being more vulnerable to mental health issues (Lavrijsen according to Silverman, 1994). Such negative perceptions about the psychological adjustment of cognitively gifted individuals are dominant among the general public, who anticipated those individuals to be less emotionally stable when they were described as intellectually/cognitively gifted (Lavrijsen according to Baudson 2016; Weyns, Preckel, Verschueren, 2021). By contrast, empirical studies comparing the prevalence of psychological problems between gifted and non-gifted youth generally do not seem to confirm such negative stereotypes (Lavrijsen, Verschueren, 2023). Overall, these studies did not find indications that high cognitive ability would increase risks for psychological maladjustment (Lavrijsen according to Lein 2021).

1.1. Cognitive health

Cognitive health is the development and preservation of the multidimensional cognitive structure that allows older people to maintain social connectedness, an ongoing sense of purpose, and the abilities to function independently, permit functional recovery from illness or injury, and cope with residual functional deficits (Hendrie et al., 2006:13). Cognitive health can be defined as the overall state of an individual’s cognitive functions, which include different cognitive abilities. It is an important aspect of overall well-being and plays a fundamental role in everyday functioning, personal relationships, and quality of life.

Cognitive health is an essential part for every individual to adapt and navigate through their daily lives effectively. Healthy cognitive functioning allows an individual to retain and recall information, focus on different kinds of tasks, make decisions, and solve problems efficiently. Moreover, cognitive health contributes a lot to emotional well-being, as it helps to regulate emotions and manage everyday stress effectively. Good brain health enables individuals to comprehend their abilities and adjust their cognitive, psychological, emotional, and behavioral functioning according to various life events to cope optimally (Puri, Shaheen, Grover, 2023).

Multiple factors affect the brain’s health, such as age-related changes in the brain, injuries, mood disorders, substance abuse, and diseases (Anstey, Cherbuin, Herath, 2013). Some factors cannot be changed, such as genetics, and age, but others can be modified and changed through lifestyle choices and interventions. Those modifiable lifestyle factors include diet and physical activity, sleep, social engagement, stress management, cognitive activity, smoking, and alcohol consumption. All of these may stabilize or improve declining cognitive function.

So, several factors can influence cognitive health throughout an individual’s lifespan.

1. *Genetics: Genetic factors play a significant role in cognitive health. Certain genetic variations can increase the risk of cognitive decline/impairment and neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer’s disease (Bugarski, Semnic, 2009). However, genetic predisposition does not determine an individual’s cognitive health entirely, as environmental factors also can play an important role in shaping our cognitive health.*
2. *Individual’s Age: As individuals age, cognitive functions tend to decline physiologically with time. Less functional memory capacity, slower processing speeds, shorter attention spans, and a reduction in working memory capacity are characteristics of age-related cognitive decline. Other things like lifestyle factors and cognitive stimulation can help slow down this decline and help to maintain cognitive health, specifically in older age (Bugarski Ignjatović et al., 2015).*
3. *Lifestyle Factors: Various lifestyle factors play a significant role in shaping cognitive health. Regular physical exercise and adequate sleep can help to improve cognitive function. A healthy food known as a “Mediterranean diet” which is rich in fruits, vegetables, whole grains, and omega-3 fatty acids also provides support to cognitive health. Some other factors like stress management, and social engagement can contribute a lot to cognitive well-being.*
4. *Role of Education and Cognitive Stimulation: With education and cognitive engagement, there is a lower chance of cognitive decline*

and better cognitive performance. Continuous learning, and engaging in mentally stimulating activities can help maintain cognitive health.

The World Health Organization defines health as a positive state of “physical, mental, and social well-being” (World Health Organization, 1948). With this definition of health came a focus on positive practices such as the proactive prevention of disease and cultivation of health-related strengths through efforts such as physical exercise, cognitive challenge, and social skills training (Gaines, 2021).

Although the concepts of *cognitive health* and *mental health* may sometimes seem to be connected, they concentrate on separate facets of well-being. Memory, attention, perception, problem-solving, and decision-making skills are all included in cognitive health, which describes the general condition of a person’s cognitive functioning. Mental health encompasses a broader range of psychological well-being like a person’s emotional, psychological, and social well-being and their ability to cope with the challenges and stresses of life. Although different, these concepts are traditionally interrelated and often have to be seen as a unity.

While cognitive health has often been included as a dimension of health and well-being, its study as a singular focus is a more recent development (Aidman, 2020). Cognitive health is one dimension of having a healthy brain. Many different terms are used to describe the basic idea related to cognitive health - cognitive fitness, mental fitness, brain fitness, cognitive readiness, etc. For example, the concept of mental fitness has emerged in the mental health and positive psychology literature (McCarthy, 1964, Seligman, 2008) to promote a positive and proactive notion of mental health. The mental health literature is focused on identifying protective factors, such as cognitive flexibility, implicated both in the prevention of mental illness and the promotion of “flourishing” (Robinson et al., 2015).

It is important to maintain cognitive health through regular mental challenges because cognitive capacity is associated with one’s ability to perform both complex and basic activities of daily living (Gaines, 2021). Regular, challenging cognitive activity can be considered neuro-protective

in that it produces increased connections between neurons in the brain, which can help compensate for encroaching Alzheimer’s disease or other age-related disorders (Wilson et al., 2002; Volarov et al., 2020; Kovač et al, 2020a). The “use it or lose it” theory of cognitive health holds that the brain is like a muscle whose cognitive strength increases with use and declines if idle. There is ample evidence supporting this theory and one of the well-known is a “Nun study” (Wilson et al., 2002).

Stimulating cognitive capacity helps individuals to stimulate new connections between nerve cells in the brain – a phenomenon known as neuroplasticity. In this way, those areas of the brain are more capable of various activities and more resistant to brain degeneration (Mateos-Aparicio, Rodríguez-Moreno, 2019). Besides stimulating cognitive capacity, positive emotions also play a protective role in cognitive health. Negative emotions tend to narrow our perspective on a situation to only its most threatening aspects (Kovač et al, 2020). On the other hand, positive emotions like pride tend to broaden and enhance cognition (Isen et al., 1987; Kovač et al, 2020). Based on such arguments, positive neuropsychology advocates an approach in which the cognitive assessment would primarily focus on cognitive strengths and not weaknesses. Focusing on cognitive strengths and promoting cognitive health has two key advantages. Focusing on cognitive strengths helps individuals accurately assess what they can do, which in turn allows for the proper deployment of strengths (Gaines, 2021). In focusing on our cognitive strengths, we are more likely to experience positive emotional states such as pride and self-confidence, which are known to enhance thinking (Gaines according to Isen, Daubman, & Nowicki, 1987). Because cognitive health is an integral part of general health, most recommendations that can be applied to improve overall health can be used for the stimulation of cognitive health such as good sleep routine and exercise.

1.1.1. Cognitive reserve

Cognitive reserve is defined as the ability to optimize or maximize the usage of neural networks when facing tasks with greater cognitive load serving as a protective factor from cognitive decline (Volarov et al., 2020:11). In the clinical population, it is assumed that cognitive reserve

has the role of minimizing the effects of brain pathology on cognitive functioning through more flexible alterations between engaged neural networks. In the earliest stages of the construct development, it was predominantly expressed via levels of education or verbal intelligence (Volarov et al., 2020:11). However, accumulated research evidence suggests that cognitive reserve is a multidimensional construct and that various lifelong activities should be taken into account when assessed (Volarov et al., 2020:11). Cognitive reserve reflects the effectiveness of the internal connections of the brain and it is a protective factor in brain damage, slowing cognitive aging or reducing the risk of mental health disorders. Cognitive reserve enables the brain to adjust and compensate for the challenges it faces. People with higher cognitive reserve have more efficient brain networks that allow them to actively cope with pathology using compensatory mechanisms (Stern, 2002). Previous studies suggested the role of cognitive reserve as a moderator effect in mental health problems such as depression (Opdebeeck et al., 2018). Thus, cognitive reserve plays a vital role in protecting the brain against cognitive decline, age-related cognitive disorders, and mental health problems. Because of this, strengthening and stimulating the cognitive reserve is one of the protective factors for overall mental health.

2. Mental health

Mental health is according to the World Health Organization “a state of mental well-being that enables people to cope with the stresses of life, realize their abilities, learn well and work well, and contribute to their community” (World Health Organization, 2021). Reference to this definition makes it clear that mental or psychological well-being is influenced not only by individual characteristics or attributes but also by the socioeconomic circumstances in which persons find themselves and the broader environment in which they live (World Health Organization, 2012).

Figure 1. Contributing factors to mental health and well-being
(World Health Organization, 2012).

- *Individual attributes and behaviors*: These relate to a person’s innate as well as learned ability to deal with thoughts and feelings and to manage in daily life, as well as the capacity to deal with the social world around by partaking in social activities, taking responsibilities or respecting the views of others. An individual’s mental health state can also be influenced by genetic and biological factors (World Health Organization, 2012:3).
- *Social and economic circumstances*: The capacity for an individual to develop and flourish is deeply influenced by their immediate social surroundings – including their opportunity to engage positively with family members, friends, or colleagues, and earn a living for themselves and their families – and also by the socio-economic circumstances in which they find themselves (World Health Organization, 2012:4). Restricted or lost opportunities to gain an education and income are especially pertinent socio-economic factors (World Health Organization, 2012:4).

- *Environmental factors*: The wider sociocultural and geopolitical environment in which people live can also affect an individual’s, household’s, or community’s mental health status, including levels of access to basic commodities and services (water, essential health services, the rule of law), exposure to predominating cultural beliefs, attitudes or practices, as well as by social and economic policies formed at the national level (World Health Organization, 2012:4). Discrimination, loss of basic human rights, social or gender inequality, are examples of adverse structural determinants of mental well-being (World Health Organization, 2012:4; Ivanović, Petrović, 2022, Radaković, 2020; Savić, 2019).

Table 1 presents a list of factors that may be risk or protective for mental health status.

Table 1. Mental health determinants – risk and protective factors

<i>Level</i>	<i>Adverse factors</i>		<i>Protective factors</i>
Individual attributes	Low self-esteem	↔	Self-esteem, confidence
	Cognitive/emotional immaturity	↔	Ability to solve problems and manage stress or adversity
	Difficulties in communicating	↔	Communication skills
	Medical illness, substance use	↔	Physical health, fitness
Social circumstances	Loneliness, bereavement	↔	Social support of family & friends
	Neglect, family conflict	↔	Good parenting / family interaction
	Exposure to violence/abuse	↔	Physical security and safety
	Low income and poverty	↔	Economic security
	Difficulties or failure at school	↔	Scholastic achievement
	Work stress, unemployment	↔	Satisfaction and success at work
Environmental factors	Poor access to basic services	↔	Equality of access to basic services
	Injustice and discrimination	↔	Social justice, tolerance, integration
	Social and gender inequalities	↔	Social and gender equality
	Exposure to war or disaster	↔	Physical security and safety

Mental health is a state of mind characterized by emotional well-being, good behavioral adjustment, relative freedom from anxiety and disabling symptoms, and a capacity to establish constructive relationships and cope with the ordinary demands and stresses of life (VandenBos, 2007). It is a key aspect in peoples’ lives, but also necessary for economic growth and social development (World Health Organization, 2021). This concept is directly related to quality of life and well-being. Its decrease or deficit

results in health issues, deprivation, and relationship problems but also in problems concerning education, employability, and job performance. Mental health is more than the absence of mental disorders. It exists on a complex continuum, which is experienced differently from one person to the next, with varying degrees of difficulty and distress and potentially very different social and clinical outcomes (World Health Organization, 2021).

2.1. Cognitive dysfunction in mental health problems

Mental health conditions include mental disorders and psychosocial disabilities as well as other mental states associated with significant distress, impairment in functioning, or risk of self-harm. People with mental health conditions are more likely to experience lower levels of mental well-being, but this is not always or necessarily the case. Mental illnesses/disorders are health conditions involving changes in emotion, thinking, or behavior (or a combination of these). Mental illnesses can be associated with distress and/or problems functioning in social, professional, or family activities.

All types of mental disorders come with a hidden cost in the form of cognitive dysfunction, including deficits in memory, attention, executive functions, and processing speed (Abramovitch, Short, Schweiger, 2021). Abramovitch, Short, and Schweiger (2021) analyzed data from all existing meta-analyses and systematic reviews of cognitive function across all disorders recognized by the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders. They included 97 meta-analyses covering 29 mental health disorders and incorporated data from more than 200,000 individuals (Abramovitch, Short, Schweiger, 2021). This research team found that both diagnosable mental disorders, as well as some common symptoms such as anxiety and worry, carry a “cognitive price.” They termed this phenomenon “The C Factor”. It is short for *cognitive dysfunction*. According to this interpretation “The C Factor” can be defined either as lower performance on cognitive tests or reduction in cognitive abilities, such as a lower level of attention or impaired executive functions. Abramovitch et al. study (2021) suggests that it can be found across disorders and that it constitutes an integral part of poorer mental health. Several studies demonstrated that cognitive dysfunction is associated with the presence of psychopathology and with overall psychopathology-related severity/burden, but not with a

specific diagnosis or disorder-specific symptom severity, in both adults and youth samples (David et al., 2008; McGrath et al., 2016). Cumulative evidence emerged in the last decade suggesting that in the context of any psychopathology, cognitive deficiencies across domains may be the rule rather than the exception (Bloemen et al., 2018, Doyle et al., 2018, East-Richard et al., 2020; Castaneda et al., 2008).

3. Conclusion

Mental health and cognition are inextricably linked and cannot be considered separately. To maintain mental health, we need cognitive health and vice versa. As it is shown, a multitude of factors contribute to each of the given phenomena, which further highlights the complexity of this relationship. Therefore, it should always be considered that cognitive health is equally important for mental health and overall well-being as all other factors that are more often highlighted as cognitive ones. The importance and place of cognitive reserve as a key resource that contributes to cognitive strength and acts as a very important protective factor should be highlighted here. Although often neglected and occasionally forgotten, the cognitive reserve has an important place in the maintenance of both cognitive and mental health. Higher cognitive and brain reserve may be protective factors for mental health issues. Future considerations should certainly be directed toward promoting the given protective factor.

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